

Berner Fachhochschule
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Research Data Sharing for Replications and Follow-Up Studies

*A Best Practice Example from
Leadership Research*

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► Love Data Week, 16th of February, 2023

Agenda

- ▶ Introduction
- ▶ Replication Studies
- ▶ Original paper
- ▶ Data (Project TALENT)
- ▶ Replication process
- ▶ Results
- ▶ Learnings
- ▶ Open Discussion

Introduction

Scientific Credibility Crisis

- ▶ Two incidents in fall/winter 2011/12:
 - ▶ Diederik Stapel
 - ▶ Dutch psychologists faking experimental data
 - ▶ Ulrich Lichtenthaler
 - ▶ German management researcher facing self-plagiarism and “statistical irregularities”
 - ▶ Only tip of the iceberg

QRPs - Misconduct

TABLE 2
QUESTIONABLE RESEARCH PRACTICES (MISCONDUCT)

	NEVER	RARELY	SOMETIMES	OFTEN	VERY OFTEN	TOTAL
HOW OFTEN HAVE YOU ENCOUNTERED THE CASE THAT AN AUTHOR...						
... FABRICATED OR FALSIFIED DATA (EDITORS)	125 63.78%	53 27.04%	11 5.61%	6 3.06%	1 0.51%	196
... FABRICATED OR FALSIFIED DATA (REVIEWERS)	648 84.82%	87 11.39%	18 2.36%	7 0.92%	4 0.52%	764
... DELETED DATA IN AN UNJUSTIFIED WAY (EDITORS)	99 50.51%	58 29.59%	25 12.76%	11 5.61%	3 1.53%	196
... DELETED DATA IN AN UNJUSTIFIED WAY (REVIEWERS)	537 70.47%	156 20.47%	47 6.17%	17 2.23%	5 0.66%	762
... DECEPTIVELY OR MISLEADINGLY REPORTED STUDY DESIGN (EDITORS)	72 36.73%	62 31.63%	38 19.39%	18 9.18%	6 3.06%	196
... DECEPTIVELY OR MISLEADINGLY REPORTED STUDY DESIGN (REVIEWERS)	388 50.99%	215 28.25%	120 15.77%	30 3.94%	8 1.05%	761
... CHANGED OR OMITTED DATA POINTS IN A STUDY (EDITORS)	103 52.82%	48 24.62%	27 13.85%	14 7.18%	3 1.54%	195
... CHANGED OR OMITTED DATA POINTS IN A STUDY (REVIEWERS)	511 67.33%	162 21.34%	58 7.64%	21 2.77%	7 0.92%	759

Hoover & Hopp (2017)

Scientific Credibility Crisis

- ▶ Credibility crisis in social sciences (Amrhein et al., 2017)
 - ▶ Venture capitalists do not rely on published scientific results (Osherovich, 2011)
 - ▶ Fake news and alternative facts lower public trust in sciences (Hendriks et al., 2016)

Pruschak (2021)

Open data increases transparency

- ▶ Open data enables (direct) replications
 - ▶ Verification of assumptions, outlier treatments, ...
 - ▶ Assessing validity of results with varying model specification
 - ▶ Replications good starting point for follow-up research
- ▶ Open data raises integrity in the review process
 - ▶ Submission of data files (& code) for review
 - ▶ Reviewers can evaluate analysis

Replication Studies

Types of Replications

Direct replication

- Repetition of an earlier experiment / study using the original or identically collected data
- Same theory and models

- Verification of scientific facts
- They do not increase our understanding
- Have limited confirmatory power

«Why publish something that is already known?»

Hard to publish due to editorial novelty-bias in the social sciences

Conceptual replication

- Testing hypotheses from earlier studies with a different empirical set-up.
- Same research question with new research approach, different data and models

- Verification of scientific facts
- Extends understanding through introduction of differences.

Represent a balance between confirmation and novelty. Rather fulfil the implicit publication rules

Follow-up study (extension)

- Starts with a direct replication of an earlier experimental condition / study
- Additional experimental conditions, measures, models and / or data is added to assess a new hypothesis that not been tested before

- Verification of scientific facts
- Produces additional understanding by testing new hypotheses

Schmidt, S. (2009). Shall we really do it again? The powerful concept of replication is neglected in the social sciences. *Review of General Psychology*, 13(2), 90–100.

Kaiser – 1

- ▶ It pays to be Herr Kaiser (Silberzahn, & Uhlmann, 2013)

Research Article

It Pays to Be Herr Kaiser: Germans With Noble-Sounding Surnames More Often Work as Managers Than as Employees

Raphael Silberzahn¹ and Eric Luis Uhlmann²

¹Organizational Behaviour & Information Systems, Judge Business School, University of Cambridge, and ²Management and Human Resources Department, HEC Paris

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pss.sagepub.com

≡ t-online.

SUCHBEGRIFF EINGEBEN...

Adlig klingende Namen helfen bei der Karriere

17.10.2013, 17:45 Uhr | bv, t-online.de

Nachnamen können auf die Träger und die Umwelt abfärben: Herr Ritter hat gute Karrierechancen (Quelle: Thinkstock by Getty-Images)

Kaiser – 2

- ▶ Matched-Name Analysis reveals no evidence of name-meaning effect (Silberzahn, Simonsohn, & Uhlmann, 2014)

Commentary

Matched-Names Analysis Reveals No Evidence of Name-Meaning Effects: A Collaborative Commentary on Silberzahn and Uhlmann (2013)

Raphael Silberzahn¹, Uri Simonsohn², and Eric Luis Uhlmann³

¹Organisational Behaviour & Information Systems, Judge Business School, University of Cambridge;

²The Wharton School, University of Pennsylvania; and ³Management and Human Resources Department, HEC Paris School of Management

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SPIEGEL, Job & Karriere

In Kooperation mit **manager**

Nachnamen-Psychologie

Krüger oder Kaiser - Karriere geht immer

Nachnamen wie Kaiser und König helfen der Karriere, berichteten Forscher kürzlich. Bauer oder Meier hätten es schwerer auf dem Weg ins Management. Nun kassieren die Wissenschaftler das Ergebnis ein - aus gutem Grund.

31.05.2014, 14:47 Uhr

Alles klar, Herr König? Edel klingende Nachnamen verbessern doch nicht die Karrierechancen. Foto: Corbis

Es klingt ja plausibel: Menschen mit edel klingendem Nachnamen wie Frau Fürst und Herr Baron finden eher ihren Weg in eine Führungsposition als Menschen mit gewöhnlicheren Nachnamen wie Frau Schuster oder Herr Fischer - das berichteten Forscher vor Kurzem im Fachblatt "Psychological Science". Raphael Silberzahn und Eric Luis Uhlmann hatten 223.000 Datensätze des Karriere-Netzwerks Xing ausgewertet, ihre Daten untermauerten anscheinend den Effekt. "Es zählt sich aus, Herr Kaiser zu sein", titelten sie über ihrem Fachartikel. Auch SPIEGEL ONLINE berichtete über die Studie.

Original study

Leadership Skills and Wages (Kuhn & Weinberger 2005)

- ▶ “Is there such a thing as leadership skill?” (396)
 - ▶ Leadership positions in high school = higher earnings in later life (for white males)
 - ▶ Bill Gates: Captain of Chess Team
 - ▶ Steve Balmer: Math Club President
 - ▶ Lloyd Blankfein: Captain of Swimming Team
- ▶ Importance of leadership development (Day et al., 2014)
 - Employers focus on soft skills (Andrews, & Higson, 2008; Palmer et al., 2001)
 - Leadership trainings (Kaiser, & De Vries, 2000; Manolis et al., 2009)
 - Leadership in high school advantage in top college admission (Morse, 2000)

Methods & Results

▶ Methods

- ▶ Data from Project TALENT (1960), NLS72 and HSB 1982
- ▶ Only for white males
- ▶ OLS models with several controls and variations

▶ Results

- ▶ Leadership effect between 4% to 33%
- ▶ Only robust for those that are team captains and those that are team captains and club presidents
- ▶ Relationship between leadership in high school and later managerial position

Endogeneity

- ▶ Traits influence leadership chances in high school **and** later life earnings
- ▶ Observable omitted selection (Hamilton & Nickerson, 2003; Shaver, 1998)
 - ▶ Observable factors that influence leadership positions in high schools and later life earnings (e.g., math skills, BMI, ...)
 - ▶ OLS coefficients do not reveal effect of leadership position, but also of observable factors
- ▶ Unobservable or omitted causes for endogeneity (Antonakis et al., 2010 & 2014)
 - ▶ Omitted variables, common-method variances, measurement errors, ...
 - ▶ Error terms might be correlated with variables
 - ▶ Effects could be over- or underestimated

Data

Project TALENT

Project TALENT

- ▶ Longitudinal study among US high school students
 - ▶ First wave: More than 400,000 US high school students
- ▶ First interview phase in 1960 (3 school days)
 - ▶ Follow-up interviews 1, 5 and 11 years later
 - ▶ Pilot follow-up study conducted in 2011 and 2012
 - ▶ Large scale-follow-up study conducted in 2016-2020
- ▶ Detailed information on numerous aspects
 - ▶ Parents education, *own education*, grade, weight, body size, dates, family wealth, personality, test, awards, skills, interests, ...
 - ▶ Employed in many disciplines (e.g., Austin & Hanisch, 1990; Kenny et al. 1979; Wise 1985)

Project TALENT

▶ Available

- ▶ Free access for non-commercial research purpose
- ▶ American Institutes for Research (<https://www.air.org/project/project-talent>)
- ▶ Strict data regulations (Signing of NDA, submission of data protection plan, no investigation on computers connected to internet, ...)
- ▶ Transfer of data via physical shipping of CD (1st time in 2018: floppy disk)

▶ Data availability enables replication studies

- ▶ Call for special issue submissions of replication studies in *The Leadership Quarterly* (Clapp-Smith et al., 2018)
- ▶ Submission of proposal based on Project TALENT data
 - ▶ Assessing original results
 - ▶ Testing for endogeneity
 - ▶ Extending to non-whites and females

Replication Process

Replication Process

- ▶ Data from AIR in February 2019
- ▶ Data coding and cleaning to align dataset with Kuhn & Weinberger (2005)
 - ▶ Substantial efforts based on information provided in paper
 - ▶ Final dataset included 257 fewer observations than original dataset
 - ▶ Descriptive statistics and OLS coefficients did not align
 - ▶ Especially later-life income differed substantially
- ▶ We reached out to authors asking for help to understand their coding
 - ▶ Catherine Weinberger sent us their code-files
 - ▶ Understand dealing with missing values (inclusion through dummies instead of dropping)
 - ▶ Manually calculate income data based on yearly/monthly income instead of using reported hourly wage

Descriptive Statistics

Kuhn & Weinberger (2005)

Table 1
Sample Means

	TALENT, Grades 10–12 (High School 1960, Earnings 1971–73)
Earnings:	
Hourly earnings	\$5.30
Annual earnings	
Leadership: ^a	
Both captain and president	.218
Captain only	.138
President only	.221
Membership: ^a	
Both on team and in club	.776
On team only	.027
In club only	.179
Math score (percentile/100)	.487
Educational attainment:	
High school only	.329
Some college	.278
College degree or higher	.392
Parents' education:	
High school ^b	.548
College degree ^c	.195
Number of schools represented	1,005
Sample size	24,041

NOTE.—In all cases, the sample includes only white men.

Hopp & Pruschak (2020)

Table 1

Descriptive statistics and correlations for KW sample.

Variable name	M	SD
Log (Hourly Earnings)	1.58	0.45
Both Captain and President	0.21	0.41
Captain Only	0.13	0.33
President Only	0.24	0.42
Both on Team and in Club	0.76	0.42
On Team Only	0.02	0.15
In Club Only	0.19	0.39
Math Score	53.15	28.53
High School	0.50	0.50
College Degree	0.20	0.40
Some College	0.23	0.42
College Degree or Higher	0.40	0.49

N. of obs. is 24,041.

Results

OLS Regression

Kuhn & Weinberger (2005)

Table 4.2: Direct Replication – OLS of KW Table 2

	Model 1 Log (Hourly Earnings)	Model 2 Log (Hourly Earnings)	Model 3 Log (Hourly Earnings)	Model 4 Log (Hourly Earnings)
Leader				
Both Captain and President	0.054*** (0.012)	0.049*** (0.012)	0.049*** (0.012)	0.038** (0.012)
Captain Only	0.036** (0.013)	0.036** (0.013)	0.036** (0.013)	0.035** (0.013)
President Only	0.036*** (0.011)	0.020† (0.011)	0.019† (0.011)	0.010 (0.011)
Member				
Both on Team and in Club	0.107*** (0.025)	0.073** (0.024)	0.070** (0.025)	0.055* (0.025)
On Team only	0.083* (0.035)	0.062† (0.034)	0.060† (0.034)	0.059† (0.034)
In Club Only	0.036 (0.026)	0.008 (0.026)	0.005 (0.026)	-0.006 (0.026)
Controls				
Math Score		0.002*** (0.000)	0.002*** (0.000)	0.001*** (0.000)
Parent's Education				
High School			0.020† (0.011)	0.011 (0.011)
College Degree			0.015 (0.014)	-0.008 (0.014)
Educational Attainment				
Some College				0.051*** (0.012)
College Degree or Higher				0.136*** (0.013)
School-fixed Effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
F-Value	23.58	45.63	34.87	39.30
p > F	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Adjusted R ²	0.160	0.177	0.178	0.189
Observations	24,041	24,041	24,041	24,041

Hopp & Pruschak (2020)

Table 2

Effects of High School Leadership Activities on Log (Hourly Earnings) 11 Years Later, Project TALENT Data

	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
Leader:^a				
Both captain and president	.054 (.012)**	.050 (.012)**	.049 (.012)**	.038 (.012)**
Captain only	.035 (.013)**	.036 (.013)**	.036 (.013)**	.034 (.013)**
President only	.036 (.011)**	.019 (.011)	.019 (.011)	.010 (.011)
Member:^a				
Both on team and in club	.109 (.025)**	.075 (.025)**	.070 (.025)**	.056 (.025)**
On team only	.087 (.035)*	.065 (.034)	.063 (.034)	.062 (.034)
In club only	.038 (.027)	.009 (.026)	.005 (.026)	-.005 (.026)
Math score				
Math score		.218 (.016)**	.213 (.017)**	.131 (.019)**
Parents' education:				
High school ^b			.021 (.011)	.012 (.011)
College degree ^c			.019 (.014)	-.003 (.014)
Educational attainment:				
Some college				.049 (.012)**
College degree or higher				.134 (.013)**
State controls and rural indicator				
State controls and rural indicator	No	No	No	No
School controls?	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Adjusted R ²	.165	.183	.184	.195

Further Analyses

- ▶ Endogeneity
 - ▶ Observable selection: Propensity-Score Matching
 - ▶ Omitted causes: Instrumental variable regressions
 - ▶ White males sample: Positive effect only for those with team captainship and club presidency
- ▶ Extension to non-whites and females
 - ▶ Positive effects for white females in PSM
 - ▶ No significant effects in Ivs
- ▶ Extension to long-time horizon (household income 2011/2012)
 - ▶ Significant positive effect of combined team captainship and club presidency

Learnings

Learnings

- ▶ Open data sharing prerequisite for conducting replication studies
- ▶ Data files alone are not enough
- ▶ Replication studies and follow-up studies require insights on coding and analysis processes
- ▶ Goodwill of original authors should not decide about replication success
- ▶ New standards for metadata allowing comprehensive and transparent documentation of not only data but also coding and analysis processes

Open Discussion

Open Discussion

